

CONSTRUCTION OF A PATCH ANTENNA FOR OPERATION AT 1.2 GHz: REVIEW AND COST-EFFECTIVE PROTOTYPING

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Abstract - This article presents the development of a patch antenna for operation at 1.2 GHz, covering everything from simulation using Scilab software to physical construction in the laboratory. The patch antenna demonstrated satisfactory performance, achieving the expected resonance. The study reinforces the importance of fabrication techniques and parameter optimization for the success of the project.

Keywords: Patch Antenna; Microstrip; Resonance; Simulation; Prototype

INTRODUCTION

The study of patch antennas has captured the attention of researchers due to their applications in satellite communications, telecommunications, and recent technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT). Patch antennas, characterized by their compact profile, light weight, and ease of fabrication, are especially suited for integration with printed circuit boards (PCBs) using conductive materials such as copper. These devices convert electrical signals into electromagnetic waves, playing a crucial role in wireless communication systems.

Impedance matching is essential to ensure maximum power transfer between the antenna and the circuit, minimizing signal losses and reflections, thus ensuring that the antenna operates at the correct frequency with energy efficiency [1].

Using Scilab to simulate parameters such as frequency, height, and width ensures precision in antenna construction, such as the 1.2 GHz antenna designed in this study. Advances like the use of metamaterials have improved the performance of patch antennas, increasing bandwidth and gain [2]. These innovations make them suitable for high-performance applications such as cognitive radio and satellite recognition, where antenna size and efficiency are critical [3].

Furthermore, antenna design reviews highlight the importance of construction techniques, which impact the antenna's performance and versatility across various frequency ranges [4]. The growing demand for compact, wideband, and highly efficient antennas has led to several modifications and optimization techniques aimed at increasing bandwidth, gain, and overall antenna performance [5]. This work aims to contribute to this field by detailing the development of a cost-effective 1.2 GHz antenna

DEVELOPMENT

The development of the patch antenna was based on the "Accessible Patch Antenna Design Methodology" class by Prof. Dr. Alexandre Maniçoba de Oliveira [6], and began with the creation of a program in Scilab [7], designed to calculate the main design parameters of the patch antenna. The inputs included the desired central frequency in GHz (1.2

GHz); the dielectric constant of the substrate (4.3); the substrate thickness in mm (1.6 mm); and the characteristic impedance of the transmission line in ohms (50 Ω). Based on these inputs, Scilab returned the constructive parameters of the antenna, including the transmission line width of 3.1 mm, the patch width of 76.8 mm, and the effective patch length of 60.0 mm; the angular width of the electric and magnetic planes, at 180°; the absolute directivity of the antenna, at 4.01; and the antenna directivity of 6.03 dB.

In addition to the parameters, the program generated graphs that were fundamental for the antenna's analysis. The first was the radiation pattern, which described how the antenna radiates the signal into space, providing a clear view of its coverage. The second were the scattering patterns of the electric and magnetic planes, showing the antenna's electromagnetic response in different directions. Scilab also produced a scaled drawing of the patch antenna, facilitating the visualization of its dimensions and understanding of the layout.

After this stage, a 2D electromagnetic simulation was performed using Qucs software [8], widely used to simulate microwave circuits and RF devices. The parameters obtained in Scilab were used for the virtual assembly of the patch antenna circuit, and the metal substrate was chosen to ensure that the simulation accurately represented the antenna's electromagnetic behavior.

Two simulations were conducted in Qucs. The first was the Smith Chart analysis, which evaluated the antenna's impedance matching, ensuring maximum energy transfer to free space and minimizing reflection losses. The second was the Return Loss Diagram, which showed the amount of energy reflected by the antenna at different frequencies, indicating its operational efficiency. However, the initial simulation resulted in a resonance frequency of 1.39 GHz, higher than the target frequency of 1.2 GHz. This deviation occurred because the schematic circuit simulation did not account for the coupling between components.

To correct this discrepancy, a simulation of the patch antenna layout was performed in Qucs. This simulation provided results closer to the antenna's real behavior, adjusting the resonance frequency to 1.21 GHz, a value close to the specified target (1.2

GHz). This adjustment was demonstrated by the return loss graph shown in Figure 01.

Figure 01 - Return loss graph after simulation of the PA layout

The second stage involved assembling the antenna in the laboratory with the aim of comparing the values simulated in the software with those measured in the lab.

For the laboratory stage, the following materials were used: a 1.6 mm FR4 board measuring 10x10 cm; adhesive copper tape measuring 5x15 cm; a female SMA connector, Jack type, with 50 Ω impedance; a utility knife; a millimeter ruler; A4 paper; a pencil; and a vector network analyzer.

A4 paper was used to draw the project outline based on the calculations performed, and the drawing was then transferred to the copper tape. During the lab work, it was observed that the available copper tape was not large enough to assemble the patch antenna in a single piece. Therefore, it was necessary to build it in two parts, using two tapes and adhering them to the opposite side of the FR4 board. To attach the copper tape, the center line of the board was marked, positioning the tapes so that each would cover the area from the center to the lateral edge of the board. Size and position adjustments were made using a utility knife. Next, the copper tapes were joined by soldering with tin to ensure a solid connection and to avoid the capacitive effect generated between the copper tapes and the glue core formed between them. After this process, the SMA connector was soldered, connecting the copper tape to the copper of the FR4 board, as shown in Figure 02.

Figure 02 - Result of the final manufacture of the antenna.

The board was connected to the vector network analyzer, and the instrument was calibrated before measurements using a kit containing a 50 Ω impedance terminal, short, and open connectors. The

standard sequence was followed: open connector (open), short (short), and finally, 50 Ω load (load). The measurements were displayed on the Smith Chart and the return loss diagram. Although the expected frequency was 1.2 GHz, distortions in the measurements resulted in 1.25 GHz in Figure 03.

Figure 03 - Result measured using the VNA.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Analyzing the obtained results, it was possible to observe the expected behavior of the antenna, as simulated in Qucs, with a characteristic resonance very close to 1.2 GHz. However, due to inaccuracies in the cutting and splicing of the copper tapes, whose soldering did not achieve ideal conductivity, and potential damage caused by handling during the antenna's physical construction, some noisy resonances were detected by the vector network analyzer, resulting in a frequency of 1.25 GHz.

When using the frequency of 1.2 GHz, the antenna size exceeded our initial expectations, leading us to review some stages of the manufacturing process. To optimize the design and maintain economic viability, it was necessary to join two copper tapes, ensuring both functionality and performance of the antenna. This adjustment not only met the size requirements but also demonstrated the project's flexibility in adapting to practical manufacturing needs. The results confirmed that the patch antenna met the requirements for compactness and easy prototyping, proving to be feasible in terms of cost and manufacturing.

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